

First record of *Solenosthedium bilunatum* (Lefèbvre, 1827) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Scutelleridae) in Bosnia and Herzegovina

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Solenosthedium bilunatum* (Lefèbvre, 1827) in Bosnia and Herzegovina is reported. Information on the known distribution of *S. bilunatum* in Europe is summarised.

KEY WORDS: *Solenosthedium bilunatum*, first record, distribution, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Mediterranean Region.

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Up to now, the Mediterranean scutellerid *Solenosthedium bilunatum* (Lefèbvre, 1827) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Scutelleridae) has been reported from the following European countries: Albania, Croatia (mainland, Korčula), Cyprus, France (mainland, Corsica), Greece (mainland, Crete), Italy (mainland, Sardinia, Sicily, Ustica), Malta, Portugal and Spain (mainland, Ibiza, Mallorca) (Misja, 1973; Josifov, 1986; Matocq & Pluot-Sigwalt, 2002; Göllner-Scheiding, 2006; Gogala, 2008; Aukema et al., 2013; Dusoulier et al., 2016; Ramsay, 2019; Škorput et al., 2019; van der Heyden, 2020, 2021).

Now, the first record of *S. bilunatum* in

Bosnia and Herzegovina can be reported: On 13.02.2023, a single specimen was photographed by Luka Marić south of Mostar, located in the southern part of the country (Fig. 1). The specimen was found in a house in a residential area situated on grassland in the Mostar valley, surrounded by karst hills (Luka Marić, pers. comm.). Several photographs of the specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Marić, 2023).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Solenosthedium bilunatum* (Lefèvre, 1827), near Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina, 13.02.2023. (Photo: Luka Marić).